

AN EFFICIENT DATA ANALYSIS FRAMEWORK IN BIG DATA

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Abstract:

Big data refers to huge volume of data. Big data is the process of handling large datasets. In today's scenario, data is growing exponentially faster than ever so the concept of Big data has emerged. It can perform data storage, data analysis, and data processing as well as data management techniques in parallel. Big data can process several peta bytes (10^{15}) of data in seconds. It can handle both structured and unstructured data at a time. The aim of this project is to use the classification technique before mapping the tasks into the resources. For mapping the tasks, MapReduce programming model is used which reduces the workload on the resources. The MapReduce will take more time to decide the resource for performing the tasks which is to be allocated. Parallel Database technology is used to increase the performance of Big data because it allocate the tasks in parallel into the resources.

In this model, for classifying the tasks, Ensemble Classifier is used. An Ensemble Classifier is the group of different classifiers which make the classifiers to process in parallel and also shares the knowledge of fastest processing classifier to others. The Support Vector Machine, Decision Tree and K-Nearest Neighbor are the classifiers used to produce an Ensemble Classifier. Therefore, the data's will be processed with minimal scheduling time (the map class will not take time to decide to which resource the task has to be allocated). Along with Ensemble Classifier, Map Reduce model and Parallel Database Technology is used which increases the efficiency and throughput of Big Data by reducing the scheduling time.

Keywords— *MapReduce, Hadoop, EnsembleClassifier, Parallel Database*

1.INTRODUCTION

Big data is capable of handling large datasets at a time. It can perform data storage, data analysis, and data processing and data management techniques in parallel. Big data can process several peta bytes (10^{15}) of data in seconds. It can handle both structured and unstructured data at a time. Big data spends 70% of the time on gathering and retrieving the data and remaining 30% of the time is spend on analyzing the data. Big data can process even several peta bytes of data in seconds. Big data analytics will be most useful for hospital management and government sectors especially in climate condition monitoring. There are three characteristics of big data namely volume, velocity and variety. The characteristics are explained in detail below.

- *Volume*

Many factors contribute to the increase in data volume. Volume refers to the sense of storage in Big data. For example, in facebook 2.5 peta bytes of data are processed per day. Through the internet 2.5 Quintillion (10^{27}) bytes of data are processed per day. In order to store those large amounts of data we use Bigdata.

- *Velocity*

Data is streaming in at unprecedented speed and must be dealt with in a timely manner. Velocity refers to the speed and performance of Big data. For example, internet can process only 4-5 Mb of data per second but in Big data 10Mb of data can be processed per second.

- *Variety*

Data today comes in all types of formats. Variety refers to the types of data used in Big data. Structured data refers to numeric data in traditional databases. Unstructured data like text documents, email, video, audio, stock ticker data and financial transactions. For example, in Data warehousing and Data Mining either structured or unstructured data can be used. But in Big data both structured and unstructured data can be used at a time.

A. *Hadoop*

Hadoop is the most popular open source framework used in Big data to handle large datasets. It is a batch oriented system. Hadoop is used to analyze user interaction data. It is linear

scalable on low cost commodity hardware. It is designed to parallelize data processing across computing nodes to speed computations and hide latency.

B. Hadoop Architecture

The architecture of Hadoop consists of one master node and many slave nodes. In the master node there will be a MapReduce model which is used for computation purpose and a Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS) which is used to store large amount of data. Also in each slave node there will be a Map Reduce as well as HDFS. In the Map Reduce, the master node will take care of allocating the tasks to the slave nodes for processing. The HDFS in the master node will allocate the storage space to each slave node and also keeps track of where each data is located. Once the slave node finishes the given tasks it will send the results back to the master node. There will be commodity hardware in the Hadoop architecture which is used to improve the system's performance.

Fig. 1 Architecture of Hadoop

HDFS

HDFS is the storage component of Hadoop and is based on Google's Google File System (GFS). It is optimized for high throughput and works best when reading and writing large files. The blocks are replicated to nodes throughout the cluster based on the replication factor (default is 3). Replication increases reliability and performance. The architecture of HDFS consists of three daemons: They are:

- NameNode (Master)

- Secondary NameNode (Master)
- DataNode (Slave)

NameNode

The NameNode manages the filesystem namespace. It maintains the filesystem and the metadata for all the files. The namenode also knows the datanodes on which all the blocks for a given file are located, however, it does not store block locations persistently, since this information is reconstructed from datanodes when the system starts. Without the namenode, the filesystem cannot be used. For this reason, it is important to make the namenode resilient to failure, and Hadoop provides two mechanisms for this.

Secondary NameNode

Secondary namenode does not act as a namenode. Its main role is to periodically merge the namespace image with the edit log to prevent the edit log from becoming too large. The secondary namenode usually runs on a separate physical machine, since it requires plenty of CPU and as much memory as the namenode to perform the merge.

DataNode

Datanodes are the workhorses of the file system. The actual contents of the file are stored as blocks. They store and retrieve blocks and they report back to the namenode periodically with lists of blocks that they are storing. Datanodes must send block reports to both namenodes since the block mappings are stored in a namenode's memory, and not on disk.

C. MapReduce

MapReduce was introduced by Google in 2004 for executing set of functions against large amount of data. It is a software framework for processing large datasets in a distributed fashion over several machines. The core idea behind MapReduce is mapping the dataset into collection of key/value pair and then reducing all pairs with same key.

- *Map Step*

The master node takes the input, divides it into smaller sub-problems and distributes them to worker nodes. A worker node processes the smaller problem and passes the answer back to its master node.

- *Reduce Step*

The master node collects the answer to all the sub-problems and combines them in some way to form the output.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

In the literature support, the various research papers are surveyed to find the problems in Big data and also to find the solutions for solving those problems. In data mining and data warehousing , 95% of the time is spend on gathering and retrieving the data and only 5% of the time is spend on analyzing the data. Data mining and data warehousing cannot process large amount of data in parallel. It analyses the data by using application software. Multidimensional database system is used for storing and managing the data in Data mining and data warehousing. Data mining is a single technology which applies many older computational techniques from statistics, machine learning and pattern recognition. To overcome the above problems we use Big Data. Big Data processes large amount of data by using MapReduce Technology and Parallel Database Technology is combined with MapReduce in order to perform parallel computation. The following research papers are discussed below.

TABLE I

S.No	Approaches	Functionalities
1	Exploration on Big Data Oriented Data Analyzing and Processing Technology	Big Data integrates storage, analysis,management, processing and application together in parallel with the help of MapReduce and Parallel Database Technology so that the efficiency of large amount of data is improved
2	Algorithm and Approaches to Handle	Inorder to improve efficiency and performance of computation we combine genetic algorithm and decision tree

	Large Data-A Survey	algorithm which lead to less time and space complexity so that the efficiency and performance of computation is improved.
3	MapReduce: Simplified Data Processing on Large Clusters	In order to simplify the processing of data on large clusters, inter-machine communication has been used to make the efficiency high and also to minimize the time consumption so that large datasets can be processed quickly.
4	Dynamo: Amazon's Highly Available Key-Value Store	MapReduce programming model uses the concept of key/value pair to perform computation for large amount of data because Key-value storage system, data versioning and partitioning algorithm is used to provide reliability which highly increases scalability, reliability and durability when large amount of data is used.
5	Knowledge Mining in Supervised and unsupervised Assessment Data of Students Performance	The overall performance of the students are assessed using data mining techniques such as association rule mining technique and apriori algorithm in which the overall idea of the institution, curriculam, academics are clearly observed.
6	A Library of Constructive Skeleton for Sequential style of Parallel Programming	Constructive algorithm is used in sequential style, but in parallel programming model skeleton library, SkeTo is used. It has high description power which can be extended in a compatible way and also supports sequential style of parallel programming.
7	Compression, Clustering	PROXIMUS framework is used for reducing large datasets

	and Pattern Discovery in Very High Dimensional Discrete Attribute Datasets	into smaller datasets. PROXIMUS use both sub sampling and compression of data before applying computationally expensive algorithms. It improves performance and scalability by means of algebraic technique and data structure.
8	N. Beckmann, H. -P. Kriegel, R. Schneider, and B.Seeger, “The R*-Tree: An Efficient and Robust AccessMethod for Points and Rectangles,” Proc. ACM SIGMOD, May 1990.	The R*-tree algorithm is very attractive because it efficiently supports the point and spatial data in parallel and the implementation cost is slightly higher than other R-tree algorithm .The search time is $O(3^d)$.
9	S. Arya, D. Mount, N. Netanyahu, R. Silverman, A. Wu, “An Optimal Algorithm for Approximate Nearest Neighbor Searching in Fixed Dimensions, ” Proc. Fifth Symp. Discrete Algorithm (SODA), 1994, pp. 573-582.	The nearest neighbor technique is implemented in which searching an object is expensive in high dimensional data space. It is highly time consuming. The search time is $O(dn \log n)$.
10	Lawrence O. Hall,	The decision tree algorithm is implemented which is simple,

	NiteshChawla, Kevin W. Bowyer,“Decision Tree Learning on Very Large Data Sets”,IEEE, Oct 1998	fast and produce accurate results. In this approach the rules for an agent is generated from a large training set.
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III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The classification technique is used to classify the whole dataset before mapping the tasks into the resources so that it reduce the time span, whereas during later period each and every data of whole dataset were analyzed individually and then mapped into the resources which consumes more time to complete the task. To classify and analyze the data before mapping, an Ensemble Classifier is used along with MapReduce model and Parallel Database technology to increase the efficiency and throughput of Big data.

Earlier each and every data were analyzed individually, so it takes more time to decide to which resource the tasks has to be allocated. In the MapReduce model, the map step will map the tasks into the resources based on the key/value pair to perform computation and the reduce step will aggregate all the results from the map step and finally produce a single output. The Parallel Database Technology is used to perform the computation of large data in parallel which also improves the performance of Big data. The input in this project will be the large dataset in which the whole dataset will be classified and analyzed before mapping the tasks into the resources by reducing the time span to analyze the data.

For classifying the tasks, Ensemble Classifier is used. An Ensemble Classifier is the group of different classifiers which make the classifiers to process in parallel and also shares the knowledge of fastest processing classifier to others. Therefore, the data’s will be processed with minimal scheduling time (the map class will not take time to decide to which resource the task has to be allocated). Along with Ensemble Classifier, Map Reduce model and Parallel Database

Technology is used which increases the efficiency and throughput of Big Data by reducing the scheduling time.

Fig. 2 Proposed Architecture

A. Ensemble Classifier

An Ensemble Classifier is a group of different classifiers in which the classifiers will be made to perform in parallel and the knowledge of the fastest processing classifier will be shared to other classifiers. An Ensemble classifier will give more accurate results when compared to other individual classifiers. The dataset will be loaded into an Ensemble Classifier. There are three classifiers used namely Support Vector Machine, K-Nearest Neighbor and Decision Tree.

SVM are supervised learning algorithms that analyze data and recognize patterns, used for classification and regression analysis. The basic SVM takes a set of input data and predicts, for each given input, which of two possible classes forms the output, making it a non-probabilistic binary linear classifier. The SVM checks the incoming dataset and verifies whether the data is knowledgeable data or not. If the incoming data is a knowledgeable data then the support vector machine will support the incoming data to proceed for processing. If the incoming data is a new data then that data will be analyzed by the SVM. After analyzing the

new data that data can be used for further processing.

Decision Tree Classifier is a simple and widely used classification technique. It applies a straightforward idea to solve the classification problem. Decision Tree Classifier poses a series of carefully crafted questions about the attributes of the test record. Each time it receives an answer, a follow-up question is asked until a conclusion about the class label of the record is reached. The Decision Tree classifier will look for the incoming dataset and will split the dataset based on the category wise. It splits the attributes in the dataset. The attribute which has the highest information gain will be chosen as a splitting attribute.

The K-NN is a non-parametric method for classification and regression that predicts objects' "values" or class memberships based on the k closest training examples in the feature space. K-NN is a type of instance-based learning, or lazy learning where the function is only approximated locally and all computation is deferred until classification. The k -nearest neighbor algorithm is amongst the simplest of all machine learning algorithms: an object is classified by a majority vote of its neighbors, with the object being assigned to the class most common amongst its k nearest neighbors (k is a positive integer, typically small). If $k = 1$, then the object is simply assigned to the class of that single nearest neighbor. The incoming dataset will be analyzed by K-NN and if the data is similar to the data present in the nearest neighbor then that data will be accepted and processed. If the incoming data is not similar to the data present in nearest neighbor then that data will be analyzed for further processing.

B. MapReduce and Parallel Database Technology

An efficient data analysis framework is constructed using MapReduce programming model and Parallel Database Technology. MapReduce programming model is established to map the incoming tasks into the resources and also greatly reduces the workloads of the resources. Parallel Database Technology is used for the processing of the tasks to be done in parallel by utilizing the resources efficiently, thereby increasing the performance of Big data.

The Map technology mainly processes a group of input data record and distributes data to several servers and operation systems. Its means of processing data is a strategy based on the key/value pair. The Reduce technology mainly occupies itself in summarizing and processing the result after processing the above key/value. Map Reduce is designed for mass composed of low-end computer cluster, its excellent scalability has been fully verified in industry. Map Reduce has low requirement to hardware. Map Reduce can store data in any format, can achieve a variety of complex data processing function. Analysis based on the Map Reduce platform, without the need of complex data preprocessing and writing in the database process.

Parallel computing includes two aspects: data parallel processing and task parallel processing. In terms of the data parallel processing means, a large-scale task to be solved can be dissembled into various system sub-tasks with the same scale and then each sub-task will be processed. As such, compared to the whole task, it will be easy to process. Adopting the task paralleling processing mode might cause the disposal of tasks and coordination of relationships overly complicated. Using the parallel database technology is a means for realizing the parallel processing of data information. Parallel database support standard SQL language, through the SQL to provide data access service, SQL is widely used because it is simple and easy to apply. But in big data analysis, the SQL interface is facing great challenges. The advantage of SQL comes from packaging the underlying data access, but the packaging affects its openness to a certain extent. User-defined functions which provided by parallel database is mostly based on the design of a single database instance, and therefore they cannot be executed in parallel cluster, it means that the traditional way is not suitable for the processing and analysis of big data.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the study of MapReduce programming model is done to reduce the workloads on the resources and also to allocate the tasks into the resources. The Parallel Database Technology is used to perform the computation tasks in parallel which increases the performance of Big data. In order to reduce the scheduling time for allocating the tasks into resources, classification technique is used before MapReduce and Parallel Database technology. For classifying the tasks an Ensemble classifier is used. An Ensemble classifier is a group of different classifiers such as Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier, Decision Tree classifier,

K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) classifier etc. The study of these various types of classifiers is done to share the knowledge of the fastest processing classifier to others which will greatly reduce the scheduling time. Along with Ensemble Classifier, MapReduce programming model and Parallel Database Technology is used to increase the efficiency and throughput of Big data.

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